

COMPARING ELECTROMECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYMER – CARBON NANOTUBE AND POLYMER – CARBON FIBRE – CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The focus of this research is on the potential of CNT modification for improved electrical resistance measurement based strain sensing in CF-epoxy composites. It is found that CNT addition enables smoother electrical recordings with better repeatability over a larger change in electrical resistance. Although the electrical conductivity of the epoxy resin is improved dramatically through the addition of CNTs, this effect is masked by the orders of magnitude higher electrical conductivity of the CF network. However, the presence of CNTs reduces the average CF-CF contact resistance, makes the CF-CF contacts more sensitive to strain, and leads to a more homogeneous distribution of CF-CF contact resistance throughout the CF network. The electromechanical behaviour of CF-epoxy composites, with and without CNTs, is characterized by a hysteresis, the origin and significance of which are not yet fully understood.

1. Introduction

In both carbon fibre (CF) polymer and carbon nanotube (CNT) polymer composites, strain can be monitored through the measurement of electrical resistance [1-6,7-12]. Figure 1 schematically shows the change in relative electrical resistance with normal elastic tension and compression, for both CF and CNT polymer composites. Interestingly, the electromechanical behaviour is similar in type in tension, but different in type in compression: both composites typically show an increase in electrical resistance with tension; in compression, however, CNT polymer composites show an increase in electrical resistance, whereas in CF polymer composites the electrical resistance decreases.

Schulte and Baron were the first to monitor strain in CF polymer composites through electrical resistance measurements. In their study on failure detection of load-bearing fibres in CF epoxy composites through

the measurement of electrical resistance, they found that, even without fibre fracture, the electrical resistance varies with the actual strain, and concluded that the measurement of electrical resistance could be used not only to evaluate the integrity of composite structures non-destructively, but also to monitor strain in-situ and in real-time [1]. For a variety of polymer matrices, fibre architectures and loading conditions, other research groups came to the same conclusion, e.g. [2-6]. As opposed to other non-destructive, in-situ, real-time evaluation techniques (e.g.: optical fibre sensors, metallic foil strain gages), the electrical resistance measurement technique uses an integral part of the material as the sensor, i.e. the CFs. This is a major advantage as it causes no reduction in mechanical integrity and adds no additional elements. In addition the technique is comparatively simple in concept.

Continuous monitoring of strain can benefit the long-term reliability of CF based polymer composite structures. Key parameters for such monitoring are sensitivity and precision of the monitoring technique. Given the difference in electromechanical behaviour between CF and CNT polymer composites, as shown in Figure 1, the present study looks at the influence of CNTs on electrical resistance measurement based strain sensing in CF polymer composites. By comparing the electromechanical characteristics of CNT-epoxy, CF-epoxy, and CF-CNT-epoxy composites, the aim is to evaluate the potential of CNT modification for improved strain monitoring in CF based epoxy composites.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this study were non-crimp, 0°/90°-stitched carbon fabrics (SAERTEX bidirectional complexes, SAERTEX USA) with PAN-based carbon fibres (TENAX HTS40 F13 12K,

Toho Tenax Americ, Inc.), a non-modified hotmelt epoxy resin system (AKD/LEO 2396, Nanoleedge Inc.), and a CNT modified hotmelt epoxy resin system (AKD/LEO 2397, Nanoleedge Inc.) containing multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (Baytubes C 150 P, Bayer MaterialScience). The MWCNTs were chemically modified as described in [13], and mixed with the resin through high shear mixing by the supplier of the resin systems. The electrical percolation threshold was found below 0.1 wt.%. For this, the DC volume conductivity as a function of CNT content was evaluated according to ASTM D 257, using an electrometer and a resistivity test fixture (Models 6517A and 8009, Keithley Instruments). Thin film samples with CNT concentrations varying from 0.1 to 0.5 wt.% were obtained by flat rolling at 70 °C, followed by degassing and thermal curing. The samples were 7 cm in diameter and varied in thickness from 1 to 1.5 mm. As shown in Table 1, the addition of 0.1 wt.% of MWCNTs increases the electrical conductivity of the material by more than 9 orders of magnitude, whereas the electrical conductivities for samples with 0.1 to 0.5 wt.% of MWCNTs are in the same range.

2.2. Sample manufacturing

Thin resin films of non-modified epoxy (LEO 2396) and CNT modified epoxy (LEO 2397), which were manufactured through flat rolling at 70 °C, were used as obtained. Both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites were fabricated by vacuum assisted resin film infusion, using films of non-modified and MWCNT modified epoxy resin for the CF-epoxy and the CF-CNT-epoxy specimens, respectively. 6 layers of carbon fabric and 7×2 layers of resin film were used for a [0/90]_{3S} layup, with the outmost CF layers in the direction of the specimen's long side. The layups were cured for 2 h at 130 °C and post-cured for 2 h at 200 °C. Heating rates were 2 °C/min and resin film infusion took place between 70 and 130 °C during initial heating. Upon cooling, the 3.2 mm thick layups were cut into rectangular specimens, 140 mm long and 15 mm wide, using a diamond saw. CNT-epoxy specimens were obtained under the same processing conditions. CNT content in CNT-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites was 0.3 wt.%, i.e. clearly above the percolation threshold, but low to minimize effects on processing.

2.3. Testing procedure

The electromechanical behaviour of CNT-epoxy, CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites were

analysed by measuring the change in electrical resistance during three-point bending. Using an electromechanical testing system (MTS Insight 5, MTS Systems Corp.) three-point bending load was applied at a constant crosshead displacement of 3 mm/min up to a maximal load of 700 N, over a support span of 90 mm. The corresponding stress-strain curves for 10 consecutive load cycles are shown in Figure 2, for both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites. Material deformation seems to be elastic in nature, as no apparent damage occurs. The specimens were contacted with insulated copper wires using conductive silver paint. Electrodes were placed symmetrically to the middle length at a distance of 70 mm, and the electrode area was kept constant. For improved contact with the CF network, the area below the electrodes was sanded to remove the surface resin layer. Given the difference in electromechanical behaviour between CF and CNT polymer composites, as shown in Figure 1, the focus of this work was on compression. During mechanical deformation the change in electrical resistance was therefore monitored on the compression side. This is schematically shown in Figure 3, together with a picture of a CF-CNT-epoxy specimen with electrodes. Using a four-wire set up with a digital multimeter (Models 2701, Keithley Instruments), a constant direct current of 1 mA was applied and the resistance was calculated from the measured voltage. All specimens were electrically insulated from the electromechanical testing system, and tests were performed at room temperature. To avoid any influence on the resistance measurement, no external device was used to record strain. The change in electrical resistance is instead presented as a function of crosshead displacement of the electromechanical testing system, which is proportional to strain.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Electrical resistance change in CF-epoxy and CNT-epoxy composites

Figure 4 shows the change in relative electrical resistance with elastic compression, for both CF-epoxy and CNT-epoxy composites. The CNT-epoxy composite shows an increase in electrical resistance with strain, whereas the electrical resistance of the CF-epoxy composite decreases. This difference in type of electromechanical behaviour is in agreement with results reported in literature (cf. Fig. 1). As expected for a MWCNT concentration (0.3 wt.%) to percolation threshold (below 0.1 wt.%) ratio higher

than 3, a linear electromechanical behaviour is found for the CNT-epoxy composite [14]. As for the CF-epoxy composite, a plateau is observed at small deformation. Upon cooling during sample manufacturing, the chemical shrinkage mismatch between CFs and epoxy resin leads to an internal residual stress field, with the CF being under compression and the epoxy resin around the CF being under tension. First-time mechanical loading might change the internal residual stress field, which could explain the constant resistance with small deformation, as it is possible that this has no effect on the number of CF-CF contacts, the quality of these contacts, and the electrical resistance of the CFs. A similar electromechanical behaviour (i.e. no or little electrical resistance change in CF-epoxy composites upon first-time mechanical loading) has also been found upon tensile loading, e.g. [3]. As will be discussed below, this plateau is observed on first loading only and is not seen during repeated loading. Past the plateau, the electrical resistance decreases linearly with increasing deformation. For a crosshead displacement of 5 mm, which, based on ASTM D 790, corresponds to a maximal flexural strain in the outer surface of around 1.2 %, the electrical resistance changes by 0.9 %. In terms of electrical resistance change per strain this is in good agreement with results reported in literature, e.g. [1,4]. The absolute changes in electrical resistance for the CNT-epoxy and the CF-epoxy composites, respectively, are 30 Ω and 6 m Ω . Given the difference in average resistance at zero displacement (cf. Fig. 4), however, the relative change in electrical resistance is about 10 times higher for the CF-epoxy composite.

3.2 Electrical resistance change in CF-CNT-epoxy composites

The electric responses to mechanical deformation of CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites are compared in Figure 5. Both materials show two distinct regimes. As discussed above, the CF-epoxy composite initially shows no or little change in electrical resistance with deformation. Above a displacement of 2 mm (i.e. around 0.5 % maximal flexural strain in the outer surface), its electrical resistance decreases linearly with increasing deformation. In comparison, the electromechanical behaviour of the CF-CNT-epoxy composite is similar in type in regime 2, i.e. its electrical resistance decreases linearly with increasing deformation, but it is different in type in regime 1, where the electrical resistance increases

considerably. Given the electric response of the CNT-epoxy composite shown in Figure 4, it could be assumed that the electric response in regime 1 in Figure 5 is dominated by the characteristics of the CNT modified epoxy resin. This however is unlikely, as, compared to the CNT-epoxy composite, the increase in electrical resistance at 0.5 % flexural strain is more than 3 times higher for the CF-CNT-epoxy composite. In addition, given the used electrical measurement set-up, a change in the electrical conductance of the CNT modified epoxy matrix in CF-CNT-epoxy composites, could not be recorded, as the electrical conductance of the CF network is orders of magnitude higher (e.g. at 0.5 % flexural strain: 1×10^0 S in CF-CNT-epoxy vs. 5×10^{-5} S in CNT-epoxy). As was already discussed by Vavouliotis et al., the effect of CNT modification on the electrical conductivity of the polymer matrix is masked by the electrical conductivity of the continuous CF network [15].

In CF-CNT-epoxy composites, however, the CNTs not only modify the electrical properties of the matrix, but might also influence the contacts between CFs and CF tows. Given the sample manufacturing technique (i.e. resin film infusion), a certain extent of CNT filtration by the CF network seems likely, which can increase the number of CF-CNT contacts. Taking into account the big difference between CF tow diameter and average length of the MWCNTs (600 μm vs. 10 μm), it seems likely that, in the case of CF-CNT-epoxy composites, the change in the internal residual stress field upon first time mechanical loading can have an effect on the overall electrical resistance, as the number of CF-CF contacts as well as the quality of those contacts change as initial CF-CNT contacts along the CFs and at the CF-CF contacts get disrupted. Both a decrease in number of CF-CF contacts and an increase in the average CF-CF contact resistance would lead to an increase in overall electrical resistance, which is what is observed in regime 1 in Figure 5. As it is the case for CF-epoxy, regime 1 type behaviour in CF-CNT-epoxy is only observed on first loading and is not seen during repeated loading.

3.3 Effect of CNT modification on strain monitoring in CF based epoxy composites

The electric response to repeated mechanical loading is shown in Figure 6 for CF-epoxy and in Figure 7 for CF-CNT-epoxy composites. Following the first loading, for which the electric responses are shown in Figure 5, and unloading, a representative sample

of each material was tested under repeated mechanical loading. Both composites show a decrease in electrical resistance with increasing deformation, without initial plateau (CF-epoxy) or initial increase in electrical resistance (CF-CNT-epoxy). Such a differing behaviour during the first load cycle has also been observed in other studies, e.g. [16], and, as discussed above, might be explained with a change in the internal residual stress field upon first time mechanical loading. It is interesting to note that although this change at small deformation during first-time mechanical loading seems to be elastic from a mechanical integrity point of view (cf. Fig. 2), it is non-reversible with regard to the overall electrical resistance.

Comparing Figures 6 and 7 it can be seen that CNT modification leads to smoother electrical recordings, with better repeatability over a larger change in electrical resistance. Both the smoother electrical recordings and the improved continuous repeatability might be explained with a flatter distribution in CF-CF contact resistance throughout the CF network. A change in electrical resistance due to mechanical deformation can be caused by a change in the electrical resistance of the CFs and/or a change in the average CF-CF contact resistance and/or a change in the number of CF-CF contacts (i.e. contacts within a CF tow as well as contacts between CF tows). The electric response of the CFs is likely the same in both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites. The larger change in electrical resistance in the CF-CNT-epoxy composite can therefore be explained by a larger increase in average CF-CF contact resistance and/or a larger decrease in the number of CF-CF contacts. By measuring the electrical resistance of CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites as a function of electrode distance, it was found that the calculated electrical resistivity decreases with increasing measuring distance [17]. This could be explained by an increasing number of CF-CF contacts (i.e. an increasing number of electron conducting paths between the electrodes) with increasing measuring distance. CNT addition, however, had no influence on the slope of the electrical resistivity vs. measuring distance curve. It therefore seems that no additional CF-CF contacts have been created through the addition of CNTs. On the other hand it was found that, for a given measuring distance, both the in-plane and the through-thickness electrical conductivity increased with the addition of CNTs. This can be best explained by a reduction in the average CF-CF contact resistance. As a result it can

be concluded that CNT modification leads to, first, a lower average CF-CF contact resistance, and, second, a more homogeneous distribution in CF-CF contact resistance throughout the CF network. In addition the presence of CNTs at the CF-CF contacts makes the latter more sensitive to strain. Overall, this translates to an improved sensitivity (larger change in electrical resistance for the same deformation) and improved precision (smoother recordings and better repeatability) in strain sensing. In both materials, the electromechanical behaviour is characterized by a hysteresis, the reason for which might be the viscoelasticity of the polymer matrix. As the material reacts to changes in the external stress field, its internal strain field at each load-level might be different in loading and unloading. As a consequence, for a given compressive deformation, the forces acting on CF-CF contacts would be lower during loading than they are during unloading. The corresponding average contact resistances would then be higher during loading, which would lead to a higher overall electrical resistance, as is observed for both materials. In the stress-strain curves in Figure 2, the viscoelasticity of the epoxy matrix is masked by the mechanical properties of the load-bearing CFs. With regard to the width of the hysteresis, there seems to be no apparent difference between the two materials. More research is needed to understand both origin and significance of this characteristic.

4 Conclusions

Continuous strain monitoring in CF based polymer composites can provide instant information on loading conditions inside structures, as well as assist the long-term reliability evaluation. The electrical resistance measurement technique enables non-destructive, in-situ strain monitoring in real-time. Given the difference in electromechanical behaviour between CF polymer and CNT polymer composites (cf. Fig. 1) the motivation for this work was to evaluate the potential of MWCNT modification for improved electrical resistance measurement based strain sensing in CF epoxy composites.

It is found that CNT modification, first, leads to smoother and more repeatable electrical recordings, and, second, almost doubles the overall change in relative resistance. Both the smoother recordings and the improved repeatability are attributed to a more homogeneous distribution in CF-CF contact resistance throughout the CF network, which is due to the presence of CNTs at the CF-CF contacts. The larger relative electrical resistance change for the same deformation is explained with the interruption

of CF-CNT connections at the CF-CF contacts, which leads to an improved sensitivity of the CF-CF contacts. As a result it is concluded that CNT modification can improve both sensitivity (larger change in electrical resistance for the same deformation) and precision (smoother recordings and better repeatability) in electrical resistance measurement based strain sensing in CF based polymer composites.

Although the electrical conductivity of the epoxy resin is improved dramatically through the addition of the CNTs, this effect is masked by the orders of magnitude higher electrical conductivity of the CF network. The CNTs therefore influence the electromechanical behaviour primarily through a change in the distribution and the average value of CF-CF contact resistance. It is important to note that these results were obtained by tracking the electrical resistance on the compression side during three-point bending of cross-ply specimens. Given the mechanisms behind the improvements in sensitivity and precision, however, it is likely that the same conclusions also apply to other fibre architectures and loading conditions.

Finally, the electromechanical behaviour in both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites is characterized by a hysteresis. It is argued that this might be due to the viscoelasticity of the polymer matrix. More research, however, is needed to understand both origin and significance of this characteristic.

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Fig. 1: Schematic comparison of relative resistance change in CF polymer composites (solid line) and CNT polymer composites (dashed line), for both normal elastic compression and tension, R_0 being the resistance at zero strain. Examples of references are given in the figure.

Table 1. Electrical conductivity, σ , as a function of MWCNT content, w , in epoxy resin. Reported values are averages over three samples.

w [wt.%]	0	0.1	0.3	0.5
σ [S/m]	2×10^{-14}	5×10^{-5}	4×10^{-4}	9×10^{-4}

Fig. 2: Stress-strain curves for 10 consecutive load cycles up to 700 N, for both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites. The excellent repeatability shows that material deformation is elastic in nature. For both type of materials, and three or more samples tested, first fibre fracture occurred at loads above 1000 N. Stress in the outer surface at midpoint, and maximal strain in the outer surface were calculated according to ASTM D 790.

Fig. 3: Picture of a CF-CNT-epoxy specimen with electrodes and schematic representation of three-point bending test, with all corresponding dimensions.

Fig. 4: Change in relative electrical resistance with elastic compression for both CF-epoxy (average over 5 samples) and CNT-epoxy composites (representative sample). The average resistances at zero displacement, R_0 , were $7 \times 10^{-1} \Omega$ and $2.3 \times 10^4 \Omega$ for the CF-epoxy and the CNT-epoxy samples, respectively.

Fig. 5: Change in relative electrical resistance with elastic compression for both CF-epoxy and CF-CNT-epoxy composites. Reported are average values over 5 specimens.

Fig. 6: Change in relative electrical resistance of a CF-epoxy specimen under elastic compression, for 9 consecutive load cycles (a), and the last 3 load cycles (b). The load cycle numbers are given in the legend. The arrows in (b) indicate loading and unloading. The corresponding stress-strain curves are given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 7: Change in relative electrical resistance of a CF-CNT-epoxy specimen under elastic compression, for 9 consecutive load cycles (a), and the 6 last load cycles (b). The load cycle numbers are given in the legend. The arrows in (b) indicate loading and unloading. The corresponding stress-strain curves are given in Fig. 2.